

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Nebish, A., Tello, J., Ferradás, Y., Aroutiounian, R., Martínez-Zapater, J.M., Ibáñez, J. (2021). SSR and SNP genetic profiling of Armenian grape cultivars reveals insights of their identity and pedigree relationships. *OENO One*, 55(4).
<https://doi.org/10.20870/oeno-one.2021.55.4.4815>

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE 1. List of the European cultivars used in this work

Prime Name	Short name	VIVC Code	Origin VIVC
Aledo	ALE	262	SPAIN
Alvarelhao	ALV	1650	PORTUGAL
Aramon	ARA	544	FRANCE
Blaufraenkisch	BLA	1459	SLOVENIA
Bobal	BOB	1493	SPAIN
Castelao	CAS	2324	PORTUGAL
Coarna Alba	COA	2724	MOLDOVA
Elbling Weiss	ELW	3865	GERMANY
Graciano	GRA	4935	SPAIN
Kratošija	KRA	9703	MONTENEGRO
Krstac	KRS	24930	MONTENEGRO
Listan Prieto	LIP	6860	SPAIN
Merlot	MER	7657	FRANCE
Moscato di Terracina	MDT	8053	ITALY
Pinot	PIN	9279	FRANCE
Portugieser Blau	POB	9620	SLOVENIA
Prokupac	PRO	9734	SERBIA
Riesling Weiss	RIW	10077	GERMANY
Schiava Grossa	SCG	10823	ITALY
Semillon	SEM	11480	FRANCE
Silvaner Gruen	SIG	11805	AUSTRIA
Syrah	SYR	11748	FRANCE
Tempranillo	TEM	12350	SPAIN
Trebbiano Toscano	TRT	12628	ITALY
Vermentino	VER	12989	ITALY
Vulpea	VUL	13186	AUSTRIA
Welschriesling	WEL	13217	ITALY